

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

1/11/2022 – 31/10/2025

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Project 101075572 — MARINEWIND

D6.6: Project Management Plan

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Abbreviation, Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea (project coordinator)
CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE (project partner)
EC	European Commission
ELE	ELEMENT ENERGY LIMITED (associated partner)
EP	ASSOCIATION DES ORGANISATIONS NATIONALES D'ENTREPRISES DE PECHE DE L'UE (project partner)
ESC	ENERGY SYSTEMS CATAPULT LIMITED UK 919685034 (associated partner)
GA	Grant Agreement
GAS	General Assembly
GC	General Committee (all partners participating)
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MQP	Management and Quality Plan
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project meeting
PO	Project Officer
Q-PLAN	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC (project partner)
RSE	RICERCA SUL SISTEMA ENERGETICO - RSE SPA (project partner)
SC	Scientific Coordinator
SENER	SENER INGENIERIA Y SISTEMAS SA (project partner)
SG	Steering Group
TL	Task Leader
UoY	UNIVERSITY OF YORK (associated partner)

Abbreviation, Acronym	Description
WAVEC	WAVEC/OFFSHORE RENEWABLES - CENTRO DE ENERGIA OFFSHORE ASSOCIACAO (project partner)
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document establishes the Management and Quality Plan (MQP) for the MARINEWIND project. It has been implemented by the project coordinator APRE and has been written in the framework of WP6 - Project management. This document represents deliverable D6.6 – Project Management Plan.

D6.6 is a collection of instructions and decisions regarding the project management and administration as well as the quality management of the MARINEWIND project. Its intention is to provide useful information to all project partners about the procedures that will be followed during the project execution for communication and reporting purposes.

The terms and provisions of the EU Grant Agreement (and its annexes) and the MARINEWIND Consortium Agreement will prevail in the event of any inconsistencies with recommendations and guidelines defined in the present handbook.

1 INTRODUCTION

The main objectives of the MQP are:

- First, it acts as a reference source for all MARINEWIND consortium members, covering many of the day-to-day activities and providing links to further information where required.
- Secondly, it aims to standardize various procedures and elements of the project e.g. project reports, deliverable submission etc. to ensure a smooth implementation and in-time completion of the activities foreseen.

The MQP provides an overview of the management structure and also the roles and responsibilities of the partners and defines the procedures for progress monitoring, quality assurance as well as risk and project management.

Compliance with the MQP is obligatory for all partners of the MARINEWIND project. The MQP complements and does not replace the Grant Agreement (GA) signed with the European Commission (EC), including its Annexes as well as the Consortium Agreement (CA) of the MARINEWIND project.

2 MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE

The project consortium has been carefully composed to provide expertise in various fields. Section 2 describes the governing bodies in charge of all project management activities within and the consortium, aiming at the correct and successful implementation of the project.

Figure 1: Management structure of the MARINEWIND project

2.1 Project Coordinator

The Project Coordinator (PC) APRE has the overall technical, administrative and financial responsibility for the organization, planning and controlling of the MARINEWIND project. As the PC, APRE will manage the project and will also ensure the proper handling of all financial resources. Besides, APRE provides a reliable and fast flow of information and project documentation between the project consortium and the EC.

The PC's management activities include:

- ✓ Administrative project management and submission of deliverables.
- ✓ Financial management and project reporting.
- ✓ Quality and risk management (e.g. monitoring of the project's progress and activities and deciding on any actions necessary to correct potential deviations from the plan).
- ✓ Communication with the EC, acting as an intermediary.

Name	Mail address	Phone
Mr. Riccardo Coletta	coletta@apre.it	+39 06 48939993
Mrs. Arianna D'Addezio	daddezio@apre.it	+39 06 48939993

Table 1: Contact details of the MARINEWIND coordination team

2.2 Scientific Coordinator

The Scientific Coordinator, Dr. Paola Zerilli of the UoY will check and review the quality of all the deliverables.

2.3 Work Package Leader

The project has been structured into six main work packages (WPs). Each of the WPs is managed by one project partner with high expertise in the respective WP area (see Table 2).

The Work Package Leaders (WPLs) are responsible for the detailed coordination, planning, monitoring and reporting of their WPs and tasks as well as for the coordination of the WP tasks with other WPs. They coordinate the partners collaborating under their respective WPs to ensure the quality of the executed work. The WPLs are also responsible for: (1) resolving day-to-day administrative, technical and resource issues within their WP, (2) disseminating information relating to all aspects of the work to the other WPLs to ensure a smooth coordination of the WP activities and (3) reporting to the upper levels of project management (i.e. the PC and Steering Committee). In case of unexpected outcomes or difficulties arising within a WP, the WPL will inform the PC in time. If no solution can be found, the General Committee (GC) will be involved.

WP	WPL	With contributions from
1 – Policy framework assessment and co-creation	RSE	All partners
2 – Social acceptance and environmental impact analysis	SENER	APRE, UoY, ESC, WavEC, CNR, RSE, Q-PLAN, EP
3 – Financing, techno-economic analysis and survey 8 - UoY	UoY	RSE, WAVEC, SENER, ESC, CNR, ELE, Q-PLAN
4 – Development of MARINEWIND Tools	Q-PLAN	All partners
5 – Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation	WAVEC	All partners
6 – Project Management	APRE	All partners

Table 2: Overview of the MARINEWIND WPLs

Figure 2: MARINEWIND WPs structure

2.4 Task Leader

Each WP is divided into several tasks of which every task is managed by one project partner – the Task Leader (TL). They ensure a successful and timely implementation of the respective task and its deliverables. In case of unexpected outcomes or difficulties arising within their task, the TL will inform the responsible WPL as well as the PC. If no solution can be found, the Scientific Coordinator will be involved.

Task No.	Task title	WP	Task leader
1.1	Analysis of policy and regulatory barriers and enablers to floating offshore wind deployment	1	RSE
1.2	Stakeholders database		APRE
1.3	Labs co-creation activities		APRE
1.4	Elaboration of results of policy analysis		ESC
2.1	Analysis of social and environmental barriers and enablers	2	SENER
2.2	Elaboration of results of social and environmental analysis		RSE
3.1	Analysis of financial and market barriers and enablers and data collection	3	UoY
3.2	Analysis of technological barriers and enablers and data collection		ESC

3.3	MARINEWIND Survey		UoY
3.4	Elaboration of results of financial and technological analysis and results from survey and data collection		UoY
4.1	Development of the MARINEWIND webGIS tool	4	RSE
4.2	Recommendations for MARINEWIND stakeholders		Q-PLAN
4.3	Webinars for policy makers and public authorities		APRE
4.4	MARINEWIND Replicability Plan		Q-PLAN
5.1	Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan	5	WAVEC
5.2	Communication and Dissemination Activities		WAVEC
5.3	Networking with other funded projects and initiatives		APRE
5.4	Strategic Exploitation Plan		Q-PLAN
6.1	Project Management	6	APRE
6.2	Advisory Board Management		APRE
6.3	Data Management Plan and Ethics		APRE

Table 3: Overview of the MARINEWIND task leaders

2.5 General Assembly (GAS) and Steering Group (SG)

The GAS consists of all MARINEWIND consortium partners. It will take place through planned meetings (at least once in a year) and will take all the necessary decisions as well as solving specific issues, like intellectual property rights evolving, and addressing problem-solving strategies to calm down internal disputes which may eventually arise.

The SG consists of all MARINEWIND consortium partners, including mandatory presence of the WP Leaders. It will take place through planned meetings (once per month) and will take decisions regarding the planning, monitoring and the coordination of the WP tasks.

The procedures for decision-making are described in detail in the CA.

Partner organisation	Name	E-Mail address
APRE	Riccardo Coletta	coletta@apre.it
APRE	Arianna D'Addezio	daddezio@apre.it
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CATAPULT	Ines Tunga	Ines.Tunga@es.catapult.org.uk
ELE	Tom Staw	tom.staw@element-energy.co.uk

Table 4: MARINEWIND General Assembly members

2.6 Advisory Board (AB)

The Advisory Board (AB) of leading experts will provide a review of the project objectives and results to ensure that the activities are sound, pertinent and provide a high impact to the community.

The consortium is supported by a high-level Advisory Board (Elena De Luca -ENEA; Mauro Randone, WWF; Arthur Hinsch – ICLEI; confirmed and Asst. Prof. Dr. Komninos G. Komnios, Member of the Governing Board of the Regulatory Authority for Energy; Professor Ben Wilson - Scottish Association of Marine Science; Dr Andrew Gill – MORE to be confirmed), described in the task 6.2 for further scientific validation of project deliverables and dissemination of project's outcomes and results. The diversity of expertise in the different partners and their complementarity is one of the pillars that will ensure a quality and timely implementation. Further members of the AB can be added during the first months of MARINEWIND activities.

3 PROJECT COORDINATION

3.1 Internal communication

Internal day-to-day communication will mainly be done via e-mail, telephone or web-conference calls. Close collaboration and communication between project partners are essential, especially in cases where they have to cooperate in order to perform specific tasks of the project.

To make the internal communication as easy as possible, a mailing list has been established by the PC and will be addressed in the following sections:

3.1.1 Mailing List

APRE has created a project related mailing list – marinewind@apre.it - which bundles the e-mail addresses of all project partners and is based upon a “contact list” which was reviewed by all partners at the beginning of the project. If someone writes an e-mail to marinewind@apre.it, every project partner will receive this e-mail and its contents.

The PC is responsible for the maintenance of the mailing list. Therefore, upcoming changes in e-mail addresses or personnel changes have to be communicated in advance to APRE in order to ensure an effective and successful communication between all members of the MARINEWIND consortium. The mailing list will be reviewed and updated during every project meeting.

3.2 Communication with the European Commission

The PC is the sole responsible for the communication with the Project Officer (PO) of the EC with respect to the project. Project partners should not contact the PO. Only in exceptional cases, and if the PO requires so, may a project partner contact the PO directly. In this case, the PC is kept fully informed (in written form) about the content of the communication.

The PC has the responsibility of submitting all reports and deliverables of the project to the EC. The PC also provides any additional information and / or clarification (that have been requested by the PO) to the EC. Finally, the PC keeps all partners informed about any important communication with the EC.

3.3 Document management

This section describes present processes to be used for document management and exchange between the project partners with the aim of ensuring confidentiality, security, traceability, and consistency.

3.3.1 Document repository: SharePoint

All project partners have access to SharePoint folder through a specific invitation, which was sent to all MARINEWIND project partners at the beginning of the project.

Nome	Data/ora modif...	Modificato da	+ Aggiungi colonna
Consortium Agreement	14 novembre	Riccardo Coletta	
Contacts	14 novembre	Riccardo Coletta	
Grant agreement	14 novembre	Riccardo Coletta	
Meetings	14 novembre	Riccardo Coletta	
Reporting	14 novembre	Riccardo Coletta	
WP1 - Policy framework assessment and co...	8 novembre	Arianna D'Addazio	
WP2 - Social acceptance and environmenta...	8 novembre	Arianna D'Addazio	
WP3 - Financing, techno-economic analysis...	8 novembre	Arianna D'Addazio	
WP4 - Development of MARINEWIND Tools	8 novembre	Arianna D'Addazio	
WP5 - Dissemination, Communication and ...	8 novembre	Arianna D'Addazio	
WP6 - Project Management	8 novembre	Arianna D'Addazio	

Figure 3: SharePoint structure

The PC is responsible for the overall maintenance of this repository as well as for the upload of documents. Any changes on the contact list will induce the necessary changes (invitation or canceling an existing one) regarding the access to MARINEWIND Repository. In addition, every WPL is obligated to take care of “their” respective WP folders (with respect to topicality and possible duplications). Inconsistencies should be communicated to APRE. Important documents such as the GA, CA and all final deliverables can be found on SharePoint.

3.3.2 Documents to be produced in the scope of the project

3.3.2.1 DELIVERABLES

During the lifetime of the MARINEWIND project, different types of deliverables will be developed: “Report”, “Other” and “Ethics”. For these deliverables there are different levels of dissemination: deliverables can either be confidential or open to the public. The meaning of the different terms is described in the GA. These specifications have to be indicated in every deliverable. References - if used - and an appropriate history of revisions are also mandatory.

A deliverable template, which contains the before-mentioned specifications and other important components will be created by the partner WAVEC who will upload it onto the SharePoint platform (under “WP5 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation”) so it can be used as the foundation for every deliverable.

3.3.2.2 MEETING AGENDAS AND MINUTES

A meeting calendar will be updated regularly by the PC to help partners keep an overview of the scheduled meetings and to plan meetings with foresight.

Meeting agendas - if available - will be uploaded to the SharePoint (under “WP6” > “Meetings”), so visible to all project partners, no later than 10 calendar days before the ordinary monthly meeting (5 calendar days if extraordinary).

In addition, official meeting minutes will be prepared for the monthly meetings and physical project meetings and sent to all members within 15 calendar days of the meeting. The minutes are considered as accepted if – within 15 calendar days from sending – no project partner has sent an objection to APRE¹. Once accepted, the minutes will be shared on SharePoint to the corresponding folder (under “WP6> “Meetings”).

The drafting of minutes will function as formal records of all decisions taken during the meetings. Please note that both scheduled meeting agendas and official meeting minutes are for internal use only, unless otherwise agreed upon.

3.4 MEETINGS

Meetings within the framework of the MARINEWIND project are subject to basic regulation:

- ✓ All the consortium partners (GAS), including mandatory presence of one representative of each project partner’s organization and the WP Leaders – have to participate

¹ For further information please see article 6.2.5.2 of the CA.

- ✓ Meetings will be mainly virtual and occasionally physical (e.g. project meetings)
- ✓ They are scheduled by the PC and communicated to all project partners, no later than 10 calendar days before the meeting planned
- ✓ Each representative of the partners and the WP Leaders have a decision-making power and appropriate knowledge about the MARINEWIND project

This basic regulation is to ensure an effective working procedure and the successful implementation of the MARINEWIND project.

3.4.1 MONTHLY MEETINGS

To assure a good communication flow during the project implementation as well as a successful transfer of results and synergies between all WPs and tasks, the PC APRE will organize virtual meetings open to all the consortium partners once per month.

During these calls, the WPLs and eventually the TLs will give short updates on their day-to-day activities and results to all project partners. Upcoming events and opportunities as well as management issues will be jointly discussed. These monthly meetings keep all partners fully informed about the project status, future developments and other important upcoming issues.

The rules applying to the monthly meetings are the ones established for meetings (see 3.4. Meetings), plus the fact that they will only be virtual.

3.4.2 PROJECT MEETINGS

The MARINEWIND consortium, in addition to the monthly meetings planned by the PC, plans to convene five times (M1, M10, M18-midterm, M24, M36), of which three in presence and two virtual, during the lifetime of the project. The goal is to:

- ✓ monitor the progress
- ✓ take decisions on the course of the action
- ✓ encourage partner interactions
- ✓ share important technical and strategic information

At all PMs, the progress of the project - as reported by the WPLs and TLs - and the outlook for exploitation of the results will be critically reviewed and compared to the planning described in the GA. Consequently, a change in the work plan may be proposed in order to ensure the success of the project.

The PC acts as the chairperson of every PM and will be responsible for the moderation and follow-up activities.

APRE prepares a meeting agenda. The rules for the PMs convocation and for the official PMs minutes are the same set out in paragraph 3.3.2.2 *Meeting agendas and minutes*.

Meeting	Date	Location	Hosting partner
1st PM: Kick-off	M1 = 14 November 2022	Rome	APRE
2nd PM	M11= 22 September 2023	virtual	-----
3rd PM	M18 = 8 July 2024	to be identified	Tbd
4th PM	M24 = 22 November 2024	virtual	-----
5th PM	M35= 15 October 2025	to be identified	Tbd

Table 5: Overview of MARINEWIND project meetings

4 QUALITY MANAGEMENT

The MARINEWIND consortium management perspective is result-oriented. Therefore, the success of the project will be measured by the degree to which its objectives have been met. The quality assurance methodology will follow the chronological order of the WPs and will be based on their measurable results: the deliverables and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) described in the GA.

Quality assurance and control measures will ensure that the project remains consistent during its lifetime and that the results of MARINEWIND are of a continuous high level of quality.

4.1 QUALITY STANDARDS

The quality approach proposed is based on several quality standards: The ones applying to the development of the MARINEWIND project are presented in the next figure:

Figure 4: Quality standards

Each of the points mentioned in Figure 4: Quality standards are described below:

- ✓ Periodical meetings were established in order to coordinate, implement and review the different project activities throughout the course of the project:
 - PMs with the WPLs, TLs will take place five times during the project's lifetime with the aim to compare and review the progress of the project as

reported by the responsible WPLs and TLs, and the outlook for the exploitation of results

- Monthly conference calls with the WPL and eventually TL, open to all the consortium members to assure a good communication flow during the project implementation as well as a successful transfer of results and synergies between all WPs and tasks
- ✓ For all project activities, there are specific responsible partners – the WPLs and TLs - who implement and coordinate them in a leading manner
 - The WPL is responsible for the detailed coordination, planning, monitoring and reporting of the respective WP and its tasks, as well as for the coordination of WP tasks with other WPs (see 2.3)
 - The task leader ensures a successful implementation of the respective task with the support of specific project partners (see 2.4)
 - ✓ The internal progress report will be prepared by each project partner and sent to the project coordinator every ten months. These progress reports are internal documents to monitor the project workflow and use of resources and allow for an early identification of potential problems and act as an early-warning-system.
 - ✓ Unified templates - such as the deliverable template, progress report template or risk report template – ensure a professional level of quality in terms of design and presentation in all the project documents and communications (see 3.3.2).
 - ✓ All deliverables must be reviewed internally by a quality reviewer and the PC before submitting to the EC. This will be done according to a submission and review timeline ensuring that all deliverables are of a continuous high level of quality (see 4.2.1).

4.2 QUALITY CONTROL MEASURES: DELIVERABLES AND KPIS

The quality assurance will be based on the measurable results of the WPs - the deliverables – and upon the KPIS described in the GA.

4.2.1 DELIVERABLES

The following quality goals shall apply for all deliverables:

1. Satisfactory deliverable design
2. Satisfactory deliverable implementation
3. Timely deliverable submission
4. Successful deliverable acceptance by the PO

These goals are applicable to all MARINEWIND deliverables, in the exact sequence established. The measurement of achievement of the objectives can be summarized as follows:

1. The design of the deliverable will be led by the responsible partner under the supervision of the respective WPL (if they are not leading the deliverable directly) as well as the PC.
2. The implementation and development of the deliverable will be led by the responsible partner under the supervision of the respective WPL (if they are not leading the deliverable directly) and the PC. The development of the deliverable will be assessed in accordance with the description of work in the GA.
3. The responsible partner has to take care of the timely submission of each deliverable under the supervision of the respective WPL (if they are not leading the deliverable directly) and the PC. The PC will be ultimately responsible for uploading all deliverables to the Participant Portal and on SharePoint.
4. The successful acceptance of the deliverable by the PO will be the ultimate quality goal for all deliverables.

4.2.1.1 SUBMISSION OF DELIVERABLES

As the project follows a deliverable driven approach, the partners responsible for the design, implementation and submission are directly responsible for assuring the quality of the documents.

All deliverables produced within MARINEWIND will be reviewed and circulated in a timely manner according to Figure 5 and the following procedure:

Figure 5: Submission of deliverables

- ✓ Four weeks before the official EC due date, the partner responsible for the deliverable must ensure that they agree with the WPL, e.g. on the approach, table of contents etc., and must send a draft to the WPL for a first revision.
- ✓ Two weeks before the official EC due date, a draft version of the respective deliverable is sent to the responsible quality reviewer (Dr. Paola Zerilli, Scientific Coordinator) by the responsible project partner. This draft version should already have a well-developed content, but does not need to be fully elaborated yet. This step aims to ensure a high quality of the respective deliverable as well as a timely progression.
- ✓ One week before the official EC due date, the final version of the respective deliverable is sent to the PC by the responsible project partner. APRE will proceed to upload the final version to the EC after a final review.

No.	Deliverable title	Work Package No	Lead Beneficiary	Dissemination level	Type
D1.1	Analysis of policy and regulatory barriers and enablers	WP1	6 - RSE	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D1.2	Final policy framework analysis	WP1	9 - ESC	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D2.1	Analysis of social and environmental barriers and enablers	WP2	1- APRE	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D2.2	Final social acceptance and environmental analysis	WP2	2 - SENER	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D3.1	Analysis of financial and market barriers and enablers	WP3	8 - UoY	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D3.2	Analysis of technological barriers and enablers	WP3	9 - ESC	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D3.3	MARINEWIND Survey analysis Report - First version	WP3	8 - UoY	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D3.4	MARINEWIND Survey analysis Report - Second version	WP3	8 - UoY	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D3.5	Final Financial and techno-economic analysis	WP3	8 - UoY	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D4.1	MARINEWIND webGIS tool	WP4	6 - RSE	PU - Public	OTHER
D4.2	Recommendations for MARINEWIND stakeholders	WP4	3 - Q-PLAN	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D4.3	MARINEWIND Action Plan for Public Acceptance of FOWT	WP4	1 - APRE	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D4.4	Webinars for policy makers and public authorities	WP4	1 - APRE	PU - Public	R - Document, report

D4.5	MARINEWIND Replicability Plan	WP4	3 - Q-PLAN	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D5.1	Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan	WP5	4 - WAVEC	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D5.2	Communication and Dissemination Activities Report - First period	WP5	4 - WAVEC	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D5.3	Communication and Dissemination Activities Report - Second period	WP5	4 - WAVEC	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D5.4	Communication and Dissemination Activities Report - Third period	WP5	4 - WAVEC	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D5.5	Networking with other projects and initiatives Report - First reporting period	WP5	1 - APRE	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D5.6	Networking with other projects and initiatives Report - Second reporting period	WP5	1 - APRE	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D5.7	Strategic Exploitation Plan - Strategy	WP5	3 - Q-PLAN	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D5.8	Strategic Exploitation Plan - Final report	WP5	3 - Q-PLAN	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D6.1	Meetings reports - First period	WP6	1 - APRE	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D6.2	Meetings reports - Second period	WP6	1 - APRE	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D6.3	Meetings reports - Third period	WP6	1 - APRE	PU - Public	R - Document, report
D6.4	Ethical issues Reports	WP6	1 - APRE	PU - Public	OTHER
D6.5	Data Management Plan	WP6	1 - APRE	PU - Public	DMP - Data

					Management Plan
D6.6	Project Management Plan	WP6	1 - APRE	PU - Public	OTHER

Table 6: Overview MARINEWIND deliverables gives an overview of all deliverables to be submitted in the framework of MARINEWIND, who is the responsible lead partner and when they are due to be submitted to the EC.

Deliverable No.	Lead	Due date M = project month	Submit draft version to quality reviewer 4 weeks before due date	Submit final version to APRE 1 week before due date
D1.1	6 - RSE	M12	4.10.2023	25.10.2023
D1.2	9 - ESC	M32	3.06.2025	24.06.2025
D2.1	1 - APRE	M18	03.04.2024	24.04.2024
D2.2	2 - SENER	M33	04.07.2025	25.07.2025
D3.1	8 - UoY	M18	03.04.2024	24.04.2024
D3.2	9 - ESC	M18	03.04.2024	24.04.2024
D3.3	8 - UoY	M20	03.06.2024	24.06.2024
D3.4	8 - UoY	M30	03.04.2025	24.04.2025
D3.5	8 - UoY	M34	4.08.2025	25.08.2025
D4.1	6 - RSE	M36	03.10.2025	24.10.2025
D4.2	3 - Q-PLAN	M36	03.10.2025	24.10.2025
D4.3	1 - APRE	M36	03.10.2025	24.10.2025
D4.4	1 - APRE	M36	03.10.2025	24.10.2025
D4.5	3 - Q-PLAN	M36	03.10.2025	24.10.2025
D5.1	4 - WAVEC	M5	04.03.2023	25.03.2023
D5.2	4 - WAVEC	M12	4.10.2023	25.10.2023
D5.3	4 - WAVEC	M24	4.10.2024	25.10.2024
D5.4	4 - WAVEC	M36	03.10.2025	24.10.2025
D5.5	1 - APRE	M18	03.04.2024	24.04.2024
D5.6	1 - APRE	M36	03.10.2025	24.10.2025
D5.7	3 - Q-PLAN	M6	03.04.2023	24.04.2023
D5.8	3 - Q-PLAN	M36	03.10.2025	24.10.2025
D6.1	1 - APRE	M12	4.10.2023	25.10.2023
D6.2	1 - APRE	M24	4.10.2024	25.10.2024
D6.3	1 - APRE	M36	03.10.2025	24.10.2025
D6.4	1 - APRE	M4	1.02.2023	22.02.2023
D6.5	1 - APRE	M6	03.04.2023	24.04.2023
D6.6	1 - APRE	M2	4.12.2022	22.12.2022

Table 7: Internal submission deadlines

4.2.1.2 PROOFREADING AND REVIEW OF DELIVERABLES

In order to achieve a high quality of results, all deliverables must be reviewed internally before being submitted to the EC. To share the responsibility of reviewing deliverables within the consortium, the following “quality review responsibilities” have been decided on:

Quality reviewer

Figure 6: Quality review responsibilities

Furthermore, all project partners are mutually obliged to review deliverables upon request, if this has been announced in good time by the responsible partner. The reviewers (WPLs, Scientific Coordinator, Project Coordinator) should be given at least 15 working days to review a deliverable in detail. The reviewers must be documented in the review history of the deliverable.

Deliverables prepared under WP6 will be reviewed internally by APRE and sent to the whole consortium for feedback.

In some cases, peer reviews will be assigned for major documents. This has been described in the GA. Also, the Advisory Board members will be consulted with regards to major project recommendations.

4.2.2 Key performance indicators

KPIs are measurable key figures and have a strong performance reference. They serve to monitor and control project activities and processes and thus contribute to the overall quality assurance of MARINEWIND. The GA indicates various KPIs that have to be considered and fulfilled in the course of the project (see Table 8). The PC will give a regular update on the different KPIs and their status at each MARINEWIND project meeting.

Task	Expected Results	Expected Outcomes	Expected Impacts	Target Groups
1.1	D1.1 Analysis of policy and regulatory barriers and enablers	Increased knowledge of legal, institutional and political on FOWT among policy makers	Regulations more appropriate for FOWT installations in at least 5 European Countries	Public authorities in Labs countries
1.3	Labs co-creation activities	1.500 MARINEWIND Quintuple Helix stakeholders directly involved in the Labs 15+ Co-creation workshops organised	Increased communication and collaboration among all the stakeholders in the Labs countries	MARINEWIND Quintuple Helix stakeholders in the Labs countries
1.4	D1.2 Final policy framework analysis	300+ Public authorities aware about the FOWT barriers and enablers	Creation of new regulations and processes that encourage deployment of FOWT	Labs countries and other European countries

2.1	D2.1 Analysis of social and environmental barriers and enablers	Improving 15% FOWT acceptance through Labs stakeholders (comparison between survey results at the beginning and the finish of the Labs) (at least 70 questionnaires will be collected per Labs countries)	Increased social acceptance in Labs countries	MARINEWIND Quintuple Helix stakeholders in the Lab countries, in particular industry (including fishermen and tourism) and citizens.
2.2	D2.2 Final social acceptance and environmental impact analysis	Improving 15% knowledge around FOWT and its socioeconomic and environmental potential impacts through Labs stakeholders (comparison between survey results at the beginning and the finish of the Labs)	Increased knowledge around FOWT and its socioeconomic and environmental potential impacts through Labs stakeholders	MARINEWIND Quintuple Helix stakeholders in the Lab countries, in particular industry including fishermen and tourism), citizens and policy makers.
		20% increase in stakeholders awareness of social acceptance and environmental impacts	Increased social acceptance and enhanced information on environmental impact of FOWT within the 5 MARINEWIND Labs	
		Stakeholders in MARINEWIND labs trained and more aware on social/environmental policies for FOWT	Improvement upon social acceptance/environmental issues within the 5 MARINEWIND Labs	
3.4	D3.5 Final Financial and techno-economic analysis	10% increase in cumulative investments made by European stakeholders in FOWTs [m€]	Better understanding of the risks and benefits associated and the financial tools available to further invest in FOWT	Financial institutions and public authorities in countries where MARINEWIND labs are located
	D3.1 Analysis of financial and market	10% increase in market stakeholders with increased	Lower market barriers in FOWTs	

	barriers and enablers	skills/capability/competencies on FOWTs		
3.2	D3.2 Analysis of technological barriers and enablers	10% increase in optimum deployment of offshore wind generation	Major technological systems requirements on system operability identified for MARINEWIND labs	Industry in countries where MARINEWIND labs are located
3.1	D3.1 Analysis of financial and market barriers and enablers	10% increase in optimum deployment of offshore wind generation	Lower technological barriers for MARINEWIND labs	
3.3	D3.3/3.4 MARINEWIND Survey analysis report	15% increase in financial tools and technology solutions supporting both investments and marketability of FOWT	Improved collaboration between technology providers, financial institutions and local authorities	Industry, public authorities and financial institutions in countries where MARINEWIND labs are located
3.4	D3.5 Final Financial and technoeconomic analysis	10% increase in cumulative investments made by European stakeholders in FOWTs [m€]	Higher corporate engagement and increased involvement of public authorities in FOWT investments	Financial institutions and public authorities in countries where MARINEWIND labs are located
4.1	D4.1 MARINEWIND webGIS tool	500+ accesses since the first release of the MARINEWIND webGIS	More accessible information on FOWT for all the stakeholder categories and increased societal awareness and business information leading to better policies on RES.	MARINEWIND Quintuple Helix stakeholders in the Labs countries, in particular industry and public authorities.
4.2	D4.2 Recommendations for MARINEWIND stakeholders	1.000+ stakeholders aware	Creation of new regulations and processes that encourage deployment of FOWT, new viable business models that	MARINEWIND Quintuple Helix stakeholders in the Labs countries

			increase attractiveness for financial market players and new job creation.	
	D4.3 MARINEWIND Action Plan for Public Acceptance of FOWT	1.000+ stakeholders aware	Effective and transparent citizen engagement about the benefits and potential social, economic and environmental impacts of the wider market uptake of FOWT	
4.3	D4.4 Webinars for policy makers and public authorities	#2 webinars for 250+ participants (5 languages versions)	Enhanced standardisation of processes, permits and standards	Policy makers and public authorities in Labs countries
4.4	D4.5 MARINEWIND Replicability Plan	Additional 3 EU countries applying the MARINEWIND methodology	Involvement of EU countries beyond the MARINEWIND Labs in elaborating policies in support of FOWT uptake.	Quintuple Helix stakeholders in countries non partner of MARINEWIND
5.4	D5.7/D5.8 Strategic Exploitation Plan	#3 videos, #1 Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations, #2 webinars, #1 MARINEWIND webGIS, #1 factsheet of the Action Plan for public acceptance, #1 stakeholder database	Involvement of EU countries beyond the MARINEWIND Labs in elaborating policies in support of FOWT uptake.	

Table 8: KPIs of MARINEWIND

5 CONFLICT MANAGEMENT

5.1 CONFLICTS

All disputes or differences arising in connection with the MARINEWIND project, which cannot be settled amicably, shall be first resolved by mediation and finally settled by arbitration in Brussels, under the rules of arbitration of the International Chamber of Commerce by one or more arbitrators to be appointed under the terms of those rules.

6 REPORTING

Section 6 addresses all funded project partners of MARINEWIND, who have received money from the EC and therefore have to account for it.

6.1 INTERNAL REPORTING TO THE PROJECT COORDINATOR

At the due “internal” date planned for every reporting period (see Table 10), each project partner will shortly report to the PC about implemented activities, personal and travel costs as well as other costs for goods and services.

For this purpose, a reporting template (“progress report”) has been developed by APRE that should be used by every project partner (see Annex 1). A progress report is an internal document to monitor the project workflow and use of resources. Internal reports are not sent to the EC.

At the end of each internal reporting period, APRE will prepare an overview of the current budgetary situation of the project. This financial and content-wise evaluation allows for an early identification of potential problems and acts as an early-warning-system.

Progress report	Reporting period covered	Due date
1	01/11/22 - 31/08/23 - (M10)	15/09/23 (internal)
2*	01/09/23 - 30/04/24 - (M18)	Internal: 31/05/24 EU Comm: 30/6/2024
3	01/05/24 - 31/10/24 - (M24)	15/11/24 (internal)
4*	01/11/24 - 31/10/25 - (M36)	Internal: 30/11/25 EU Comm: 31/12/2025

* The 2nd and 4th internal progress report coincide with the official reporting to the European Commission. Depending on the circumstances, no internal reporting will be requested in addition to the official reporting.

Table 9: Internal reporting deadlines

6.2 REPORTING TO THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

During the lifetime of the project, periodic and final reports must be submitted to the EC.

6.2.1 PERIODIC REPORTING

The periodic reporting consists of two individual reports and will cover the work conducted by all project partners:

- The first periodic report covering month 1 to 18 has to be submitted by the PC no later than 60 calendar days after project month 18.
- The second periodic report covering month 19 to 36 has to be submitted by the PC no later than 60 calendar days after project month 36.

The PC will provide necessary assistance, templates and further indicators in due time to jointly prepare all documents and information to be submitted. Besides the two components illustrated below, every single report must include coherent explanations for any deviations that might arise.

a) The periodic technical report consists of:

- Part A of the periodic technical report contains a cover page, a publishable summary and the answers to the questionnaire covering issues related to the project implementation and the economic and social impact, notably in the context of the Horizon Europe key performance indicators and the Horizon Europe monitoring requirements. Part A is generated by the IT system. It is based on the information entered by the participants through the periodic report and continuous reporting modules of the electronic exchange system in the Participant Portal/Funding and Tender Portal. The partners can update the information in the continuous reporting module at any time during the lifetime of the project. The structured web-forms of Part A include:

- o Project Summary
- o Researchers involved in the project
- o Deliverables
- o Milestones
- o Critical Risks
- o Publications
- o Results
- o Dissemination activities
- o Standards
- o Patents
- o Communication activities
- o Datasets
- o Beneficiaries Feedback
- o Impact
- o Impact Continuation

o Other results

- Part B of the periodic technical report is the narrative part, which includes explanations of the work carried out by the beneficiaries during the reporting period. Each beneficiary has to contribute to the narrative part as indicated in a template provided by the PC. Part B needs to be uploaded as a PDF document following the template of Part B Periodic Technical report.

b) The periodic financial report consists of:

- Individual financial statements for each beneficiary;
- Explanations of the use of resources and the information on subcontracting and in-kind contributions provided by third parties from each beneficiary for the reporting period concerned;
- A periodic summary financial statement including the request for interim payment.

The report should include explanations from each partner on the technical and financial deviations that might occur.

6.2.2 FINAL REPORTING

In addition to the second periodic report for the last reporting period, the PC has to submit the final report within 60 calendar days of the end of the final reporting period. The final report covers the whole project and is composed of a final technical and a final financial part:

a) The final technical report is a publishable summary of the entire project:

- Overview of the results and their exploitation and dissemination,
- conclusions on the project,
- its socio-economic impact of the project,
- an up-to-date link to the project website,
- project logos, diagrams, photographs and videos illustrating its work (if available).

The PC must ensure that none of the material submitted for publication includes confidential or 'EU classified' information.

b) Final financial report

- The final summary financial statement, that is automatically created by the system (consolidating the data from all individual financial statements for all beneficiaries and linked third parties, for all reporting periods) and that constitutes the request for payment of the balance in some cases (and for some beneficiaries/linked third parties), must be accompanied by a certificate on financial statements - CFS - for each beneficiary (and linked third party) that requests a total of €325.000 or more as reimbursement of actual costs and unit costs calculated according to its usual cost accounting practices.

The report should include explanations from each partner on the technical and financial deviations that might occur.

6.2.3 PERIODIC PROJECT REVIEW

The PC, with the support of the Scientific Coordinator (SC), will be in regular contact with the EC project officer to report on the project's progress in a transparent and practical manner. The EC will also undertake periodic technical reviews to assess the work carried out by the project. Such confidential reviews may cover scientific, technological and other aspects relating to the proper execution of the project. Defined milestones and the list of deliverables will be used to define the progress of the project, which will be critically reviewed and compared to the planning. Depending on the results achieved, changes in the work plan may be proposed.

The EC may be assisted in technical reviews by independent, external scientific or technological experts. This "review team" may have access to the locations and premises where the work, demonstrations and pilots are being carried out, and to any documents concerning the work executed. The project partners attending the review should be those involved in the work under review, except if duly justified and provided that the partners present can report on behalf of the missing partners.

On the basis of the review findings, a review report will be drawn up and sent to the PC, who may make observations thereon within one month of receiving it.

6.2.3.1 REVIEW PREPARATION

The following schedule is recommended for the preparation of a periodic project review:

- Three months before the review meeting, the exact date and location of the review should be fixed with the PO and should be communicated to all project partners.
- Two months before the review, the objectives of the review should be defined, i.e. roles assigned to the participating project partners etc. The meeting room and hotels (in case of physical meeting) should be fixed.
- Six weeks before the review, a formal agenda must be sent to all review participants.
- Three weeks before, all supporting documentation necessary for the review should be made available to the PO. Presentations should be finalized.
- One week before, the final presentations are sent to the PO.
- One day before, a rehearsal meeting is held.

7 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

The CA covers all IPR-related issues, including background IP/access rights, foreground IP, confidentiality amongst partners, and IP ownership/transfer/exploitation scenarios (including IP licensing/use). The consortium will manage IPR results/ownership (through the PC) and settle IP internal disputes.

8 KEEPING RECORDS

Obligation to keep records and other supporting documentation

Project partners must — for a period of five years after the payment of the balance - keep records and other supporting documentation in order to prove the proper implementation of the action and the costs they declared as eligible. They must make them available upon request or in the context of checks, reviews, audits or investigations. The beneficiaries must keep the original documents. Digital and digitalized documents are considered originals if they are authorized by the applicable national law.

Records and other supporting documentation on the scientific and technical implementation

Project partners must keep records and other supporting documentation on scientific and technical implementation of the action in line with the accepted standards in the respective field.

8.1 RIGHT TO CARRY OUT AUDITS

The EC may — during the implementation of the action or afterwards — carry out audits on the proper implementation of the action and compliance with the obligations under the GA. Audits may be started up to two years after the payment of the balance. They will be formally notified to the PC or beneficiary concerned and will be considered to have started on the date of the formal notification.

The PC or partner concerned must provide — within the deadline requested — any information (including complete accounts, individual salary statements or other personal data) to verify compliance with the GA. The EC may request beneficiaries to provide such information to it directly.

For on-the-spot audits, the beneficiaries must allow access to their sites and premises, including to external persons or bodies, and must ensure that information requested is readily available. Information provided must be accurate, precise and complete and in the format requested, including electronic format.

8.2 CONSEQUENCES OF NON-COMPLIANCE

If a project partner breaches any of its obligations, costs insufficiently substantiated will be ineligible and will be rejected, and the grant may be reduced.

10 REFERENCES

- [1] S. Sampleson, Example title of reference, Barcelona: Scientific Publications, 1999.
- [2] N. Last1 and N. Last2, Book title, London: Editorial, 2018.